

APPLICATION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS, IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND CONTENT OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the socio-economic policy of the government and the President, great attention is paid to the development of all aspects of the country's life, especially to the education of the next generation in the spirit of the ideology of national revival. Today's young people are the future of our Republic. It is the responsibility of teachers to fulfill this honorable task.

Key words

Policy, great attention, education, responsibility, highly qualified, education system, well-rounded, scientific outlook.

For this reason, great attention is being paid to the issues of training highly qualified teachers and improving their qualifications. Currently, by improving the education system, great attention is being paid to the training of mature, well-rounded, independent thinking, willing, selfless and initiative personnel. In this regard, completely new rules on types of education have been introduced. The legal-normative basis for reforming the system of personnel training and continuing education has been created. Laws “On Education” and “National Program of Personnel Training” set the task of training highly qualified personnel in the continuous education system, instilling in them a scientific outlook, a creative attitude to work, and forming high labor discipline in them.

In the book “Uzbekistan on the verge of achieving independence” in the brochure “Legal guarantee of our great future” it is stated that: “In order for an educator to become a teacher, to cultivate the intelligence of others, to enjoy the benefits of enlightenment, to grow into a true patriot, a true citizen, first of all, the educators themselves must meet such requirements, they should have such qualities”. This thesis,

in turn, requires teachers to have high professional and personal qualities. That is why the tasks assigned to the teacher are very complex, responsible and at the same time honorable.

Our Uzbekistan, which has set itself the goal of becoming one of the developed countries, is trying to introduce advanced technologies in the field of education, as well as in all sectors of the national economy, and thereby bring the content of education to the level of world standards. Completing these tasks means preparing highly qualified, competitive personnel who can use new techniques and technologies in the educational system. The following are the methodological foundations of the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”: 3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the National Program of Personnel Training”. The system of continuous education in Uzbekistan includes the following: - preschool education; - general secondary education; - secondary special, vocational education; - higher education; - post-secondary education; - improvement of personnel qualifications and their retraining; - extracurricular education. Continuous education is the basis of personnel training system. It is a priority sector that ensures the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and meets the economic, social, scientific-technical and cultural needs of the individual, society and the state. Continuing education creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a creative, socially active, spiritually rich person and the rapid training of highly qualified competitive personnel. The work of transferring educational institutions to the regional direction and changing their structural structure will be carried out.

Monitoring of development of continuous education system and evaluation of its effectiveness is carried out. Training and retraining of pedagogues for the continuing education system is a priority. Continuity of education means that a person has the opportunity to receive education from birth to the end of his life. Such a system is reflected in the “Law on Education” of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Advanced foreign experiences. Modular teaching system Modular teaching is one of the promising systems of teaching, because it is best adapted to the system of developing the knowledge and creative abilities of learners. In traditional education, the educational goals are expressed through the activities of the pedagogue, that is, they are oriented towards imparting knowledge, while in modular education. They are expressed through the activities of learners and are oriented towards professional activities. We have presented the features of modular teaching technology that are different from traditional teaching in the table below. Based on traditional teaching technology Based on Modular teaching technology.

- One-way information One-way communication (textbook- teacher-student)

- Getting information
- Memorization Mechanical memorization without understanding the meaning
- Encourage active participation in learning through thinking and practical activities
 - Two-way communication
 - Remembering information through analysis
 - Demonstrate knowledge and skills
 - Understanding and relating the content to life

The analysis of this table shows that education based on modular technology significantly differs from traditional education in terms of teaching methods and tools, its organization and results. Modular training creates an opportunity comprehensively solve the following modern issues of education. - Optimization and systematization of teaching content on the basis of module-activity ensures changeability and flexibility of programs; - individualization of teaching; - control of teaching effectiveness at the level of training in practical activities and evaluation of observable characters; - activation based on interest in the profession, independence and full realization of educational opportunities. The effectiveness of modular training depends on the following factors: - the material and technical base of the educational institution; - level of qualified teaching staff; - the level of student preparation; - to the assessment of expected results; - development of didactic materials; - to the result and analysis of the modules. In modular training, the possibility of step by step training is created through fully reduced and in-depth classification of educational programs. That is, it will be possible to individualize teaching. The following goals are aimed at the transition to modular education: - ensuring the continuity of education; - individualization of teaching; - creating sufficient conditions for independent learning of educational material; - acceleration of training; - achieving effective mastery of science. Modular teaching requires the delivery of problem-based and guided lectures that provide general information on the main issues of the subject. Lectures should focus on the development of students' creative abilities. Module practical and laboratory exercises should be created together with lectures, they should be supplemented with new material to study the content of lectures.

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